

**ANALYZING EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY
WITH MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
TECHNOLOGIES TO YOUNG LEARNERS.**

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Annotation: This study reviews the effectiveness, challenges and solutions of teaching vocabulary to young learners with the help of modern information and communication technologies.

Keywords: TEFL, modern information, communication technologies, young learners.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании рассматриваются эффективность, проблемы и решения обучения лексике молодых учащихся с помощью современных информационно-коммуникационных технологий.

Ключевые слова: TEFL, современная информация, коммуникационные технологии, молодые учащиеся.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari yordamida yosh o'quvchilarga lug'atni o'rgatishning samaradorligi, muammolari va yechimlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: TEFL, zamonaviy axborot, kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, yosh o'quvchilar.

With the advancement of modern technologies it became effortless to access any information at any time from any location. It is obvious that using this opportunity to teaching foreign languages to students, makes it more effective and attractive, the computer at the lessons of a foreign language makes it possible to implement a personality-oriented approach to learning, provides for individualization and differentiation of instruction, increases activity, motivates students, intensifies the learning process, fosters adequate self-esteem for students, and provides them with a comfortable learning environment[1].

These technologies give many opportunities to teachers and students, but in teaching young learners there can be some challenges that are related to the age, ability and cognitive skills of users. Young learners are the young students aged 7-14 years old students studying in primary school. To teach them we should know their abilities. Nowadays, even kids can easily use any type of communication technologies, however the old have limited abilities to use these technologies.

Q. Mahmood et al conducted a research on this issue and find out that teachers are keen on using all types of technology tools, but the problem was that there were not

enough ICT provisions in Pakistan [2]. Another research emphasizes how crucial vocabulary growth is for overall academic and professional achievement as well as language understanding. Deeper vocabulary retention and real-world application have been demonstrated by strategies like spaced repetition, contextualized learning, and collaborative online resources. Furthermore, media-based strategies such as image-to-text recognition and video subtitles emphasize how technology may revolutionize vocabulary acquisition by making it both meaningful and accessible[3]. The answers of young learners to questionnaires done in order to find out the efficiency of ICT in learning vocabulary of EFL, reveal the most students use cell phones, laptops and desktop computers daily to study, watch movies, communicate with friends and other type of activities and Youtube, telegram messenger, facebook and instagram are the most used communication platforms. Students have positive attitude using them and doing homework using their in Ukraine[4]. One of the communication platforms WhatsApp used to acquire English vocabulary inside and outside of classroom and the result was the usage of the platform did not have enough motivation to students both in and out of the classroom[5]. When the ICT integrated by Apps like Quizlett, Duolingo, Kahoot students actively personalized learning experiences and enhanced vocabulary[6]. Mobile devices offer alternate modalities of learning, including video modeling and aural information delivery, which can benefit learners with literacy issues. ICT can help young people overcome their fear of academic failure by making them feel more competent and adept in the ICT area compared to science education. They can serve as leaders in promoting the use of ICT among students and teachers, unlike their prior encounters in standard secondary scientific education settings. ICT integration can help kids overcome negative experiences with classroom science to generate a good attitude towards it [7].According to Juma R. Haji et al teachers positively integrate ICT in their teaching process, but they need continuing training on integrating ICT within the classroom setting[8]. CDP-continuous professional development process for teachers organizes such kind of training for each EFL teachers in order to refresh their teaching methods and approaches. Nowadays in all public and private schools of Uzbekistan each Friday is devoted to this kind of programs that assists teachers and deal with the problems they face during instructing.

When it comes to usage of technology devices in schools of Uzbekistan it is prohibited to use mobile phones during the lesson, and in most public schools ICT provision is not provided or lack the quantity for full group usage during the lessons.

Teachers can actively use technology to find out different methodologies, methods, approaches, to find out various ways to teach their students. There are many platforms that give ready lesson plans, flashcards, a plethora of activities to utilize during teaching process.

In conclusion, teaching students within the modern information and communication technologies cannot be implemented in our country like Pakistan we lack adequate ICT devices provision in schools and most students do not possess proper technology to learn the language. But teachers have open access to all information and can use different tools to find out more methods, approaches and join CDP and other training courses to refresh their teaching skills.

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